

PERFORMANCE EVALUATION OF HYDROPOWER STATIONS IN NIGERIA

¹Ignatius K. Okakwu, ²Emmanuel S. Oluwasogo, ³Patience E. Orukpe

¹Department of Electrical/Electronics Engineering, Olabisi Onabanjo University, Ago-Iwoye, Nigeria

²Department of Electrical and Computer Engineering, Kwara State University, Malete, Nigeria

³Department of Electrical/Electronics Engineering, University of Benin, Benin City, Nigeria

Corresponding author: patience.orukpe@uniben.edu

Abstract

This paper presents the theoretical determination of power generating capacities of Kainji, Jebba and Shiroro hydropower stations in Nigeria. The theoretical power output equation was developed from the fundamental energy equations. Hydrological data like gross head (H) in metres (m) and Volumetric flow (Q) in cubic metres per second (m^3/s) were obtained from the various efficiency departments of the hydropower stations for a period of 2013 to 2017. The results obtained reveal that the average power generation ranges from 298.03MW to 367.53MW for Kainji, 251.45MW to 337.24MW for Jebba and 176.42MW to 207.37MW for Shiroro. The above generation levels fall short of the installed capacities of 760MW, 578MW and 600MW of Kainji, Jebba and Shiroro respectively. Thus, there is need to increase the efficiency of these hydropower stations in terms of operational improvements and application of new technologies.

Keywords: Hydropower, head, discharge rate, Nigeria, capacity factor, power

1.0 INTRODUCTION

The economic development of a nation is totally dependent on its ability to provide adequate electricity supply to its citizens (Oyedepo, 2012). Adequate electricity supply is a necessary ingredient to economic and industrial development of a nation, while, non-availability of power has a detrimental effect on the socio-economic growth of a country (Ogundipe and Apata, 2013). Nigeria is endowed with huge energy sources like the hydro energy source which gives the country advantage to transform her economy and the wellbeing of her citizenry (Onyenekenwa, 2011). However, the energy situation in Nigeria falls far below its huge energy sources. According to Edomah et al., (2016), the Nigerian energy sector is yet to be managed and restructured towards sustainable energy development. Poor access to electricity supply in Nigeria has been a major setback for economic growth for both urban and rural dwellers (Nwankwo and Njogo, 2013; Igbino

and Orukpe, 2007). Study has shown that the Nigerian electricity demand far outweighs the generation or supply, which is even epileptic in nature (Sambo, 2008). This dwindle in electricity supply hinders the country's development which invariably affects quality of life (Mbalisi and Offor, 2015).

Harnessing the potential of hydro power source in Nigeria is a key to national development and economic growth (Chiyembekezo et al., 2012). The hydroelectric power plant is perhaps the oldest source of electric energy in commercial quantity. Hydroelectric power is a form of renewable energy that converts the energy stored in water into electric energy by the use of water turbines coupled with alternators (Mansor, 2014). Water stored in dams is potential energy, when released from its elevated reservoir; water acquires kinetic energy (energy of motion). In this way, the potential and kinetic energy of water are first

transformed into mechanical energy and then into electrical energy (Amiryar and Pullen, 2017). In every hydropower arrangement, there are two important parameters that help determine available hydraulic power inherent in the system; namely, volumetric flow and the available head (Basso and Botter, 2012). Volumetric flow or discharge is the quantity of water available in a stream or river and may vary widely over the course of a day, week, month and year (Othman *et al.*, 2017). Theoretically, volumetric flow is the rate at which a volume of

water passes through a cross section of a stream per unit time and is measured in m^3/s . The available head is the vertical distance that water falls. This head is also a function of the characteristics of the channel or pipe through which the water flows. According to Milnes (2015), it is generally better to have more head than more volumetric flow; because less water will be needed to produce a given amount of power with smaller, less expensive equipment. Figure 1 shows a typical arrangement of a hydro power station.

Figure 1: Schematic arrangement of a typical hydropower system.

It is the view of this paper that instead of building more power generating stations; maintaining the existing ones to achieve installed capacity can enhance economic development by saving several millions of dollars. Based on this assertion, researchers have tilted their direction towards performance assessment of generating stations both within and outside Nigeria. For example Shobayo *et al.*, (2014), did a study on the assessment of small hydropower potential of a Opeki River, in south-western Nigeria. Their study used mean daily flow records for several years to determine the flow duration curve (FDC) and available head for the river. Abaka *et al.*, (2017), identified small hydro potential sites for electrifying rural communities in Nigeria. Otuagoma *et al.*, (2016) determined the available head for river Ethiopia in southern Nigeria. The Dumpy level and Theodolite method were used to determine the Head (H) at the source point. Fagbohun and Omotoso, 2018, investigated the viability of Elemi River in south-western Nigeria for a small hydro scheme for a possible source of

off-grid to solve the epileptic power supply within the catchment. Mathematical methods that include statistical analysis and linear programming based on simulation techniques were utilised to evaluate vital parameters based on the data obtained from the Hydrologic units of the Shiroro power station in Nigeria by Ajibola *et al.*, (2018). Modelling and simulating hydropower plant with a view to increasing its efficiency and stability was performed by the authors in Gbadamosi and Ojo, (2015). The technical and economic feasibility of a grid connected small scale hydropower in selected city of Kulfo River in southern Ethiopia was done by Girma, (2016). Evaluating the hydropower potential of Doma dam in North Central Nigeria using optimization techniques was carried out by Salami *et al.*, 2017. In this paper, investigation of the performance assessment of hydropower stations (Kainji, Shiroro and Jebba) in Nigeria with a view to determining their generations as against their installed capacities from 2013 to 2017 is carried out.

OVERVIEW OF NIGERIA HYDROPOWER SITUATION

Nigeria is ranked ninth in Africa in terms of hydropower potential, with technical hydropower energy at 32,450GWh/yr as shown in Table 1. Table 2 also shows the hydropower potentials of different States in Nigeria. According to Energy Commission of Nigeria (ECN), Nigeria has a large exploitable hydropower potential, out of which 14% is harnessed, contributing about 30% of its total installed grid capacity (ECN, 2005). In 1976, Nigeria was divided into 11 river basins (See Figure 2) via the creation of River Basins Development Authorities (RBDA) for the combine purpose of water supply, irrigation, navigation, hydropower, etc. (Okeola and Balogun, 2017). The topography of Nigeria favours the construction of dams for hydroelectric power generation. The first hydroelectric station in Nigeria, Kanji

hydropower station on the River Niger with an installed capacity of 760MW was commissioned in 1968. Later, a second hydropower named Jebba hydropower station with an installed capacity of 570MW was built on the tail water, 97km from Kainji Dam. The third hydropower station named Shiroro Dam with an installed capacity of 600MW was commissioned in 1990 making it a total installed capacity of 1930MW for the three hydropower dams. In addition, the proposed 2500MW Mambilla hydropower station is being developed on the Dongo River near Banuf a tributary of Benue River in Kakara Village, Taraba State, the country still has a potential of about 6000MW hydropower stations (Edeoja *et al.*, 2015). Table 2 shows some states in Nigeria that has potentials for SHP.

Table 1: Hydropower situation of selected countries in Africa

Country	Gross theoretical hydropower potential (GWh/yr)	Technically feasible hydropower potential (GWh/yr)	Economically feasible hydropower potential (GWh/yr)	Installed hydro capacity (MW)	Production from hydro plants (GWh/yr)	Percentage of electricity produced from hydro	Hydro capacity under construction (MW)	Planned hydro capacity (MW)
Algeria	12,000			280	500	2		700 (p-s)
Angola	150,000	90,000	65,000	290	1,000	56	780	<16,500
Cameroon	294,000	115,000	103,000	725	2,423	99		600
Congo		>50,000		89	352	>90		180
Congo, DR	1,397,000	774,000	<419,210	2,440	5,350	99	4	43,000
Cote d'Ivoire	46,000	>12,400	12,400	614	1,800	60		334
Egypt		>50,000	50,000	2,810	11,450	20	65	193
Ethiopia	650,000		260,000	398	1,600	97	297	705
Ghana		10,600		1,072	5,169	71		400
Madagascar	321,000	180,000	49,000	105	510	72	42	350
Morocco		4,700	4,000	1,205	2,350	18	90	450 (p-s)
Mozambique	50,000	37,647	31,717	2,180	11,548	94		2,000
Nigeria	42,750	32,450	29,800	1,938	6,986	43	64	4,850
South Africa		n/a		668	904	0		n/a
Tanzania	39,447	20,000	1,789	377	1,748	85	180	>1000
Zambia	52,460	28,753	11,000	1,674	7,782	100	60	>2000
Zimbabwe	18,500	17,500		670	3,000	25	85	>800

Source: World atlas on hydropower and dams.

Table 2: Small hydro potential in surveyed status of Nigeria

State (Pre 1980)	River Basin	Total Sites	Total Capacity (MW)
Sokoto	Sokoto-Rima	22	30.6
Katsina	Sokoto-Rima	11	8.0
Niger	Niger	30	117.6
Kaduna	Niger	19	59.2
Kwara	Niger	12	38.8
Kano	Hadeija-Jamare	28	46.2
Borno	Chad	28	20.8
Bauchi	Upper Benue	20	42.6
Gongola	Upper Benue	38	162.7
Plateau	Lower Benue	32	110.4
Benue	Lower Benue	19	69.2

Rivers	Cross River	18	258.1
Total		277	734.2

Source: Renewable Energy Master Plan (REMP) (2005).

Figure 2: Map of Nigeria showing major rivers and hydrological basins.

Source: <http://www.fao.org/docrep/008/ad793b/AD793B01.htm>.

3.0. MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.1 DATA COLLECTION

Data used for this study were obtained from the various efficiency Departments of the Hydropower stations. The data collected

includes the monthly average inflow rate (m^3/s) and average gross operating head (m) for each hydropower station. The data are presented in Table 3 to 7. Table 8 presents the summary of the efficiencies of the pumps in the stations.

Table 3: Average Inflow Rate and Gross Operating Head for 2013

Month	YEAR 2013					
	AVERAGE INFLOW RATE (CUB.M/SEC)			AVERAGE GROSS OPERATING HEAD (M)		
	KAINJI	JEBBA	SHIRORO	Kanji	Jebba	Shiroro
Jan.	1551.30	1216.50	54.07	37.59	27.42	105.12
Feb.	1494.61	1335.75	34.86	36.96	28.60	102.22
Mar.	966.16	1264.80	35.55	35.86	28.90	96.45
Apr.	386.20	1229.10	26.03	34.69	29.13	93.12
May	327.23	207.58	49.03	31.88	29.16	88.26
Jun.	285.57	1012.63	185.90	30.49	28.09	86.71
Jul.	653.06	1053.58	671.97	30.44	25.72	90.82
Aug.	1631.77	561.48	751.58	32.34	26.37	94.45
Sep.	1488.63	1869.76	197.43	34.10	27.75	104.48

Oct.	1799.35	1616.90	420.45	34.72	29.72	108.62
Nov.	1209.10	1102.20	130.33	36.84	28.19	107.15
Dec.	1278.87	1284.45	74.77	37.88	27.00	104.60

Table 4: Average Inflow Rate and Gross Operating Head for 2014

YEAR 2014						
Month	AVERAGE INFLOW RATE (CUB.M/SEC)			AVERAGE GROSS OPERATING HEAD (M)		
	KAINJI	JEBBA	SHIRORO	Kanji	Jebba	Shiroro
Jan.	1346.29	1656.94	50.11	37.42	26.78	101.12
Feb.	1178.64	1199.71	23.61	36.14	28.47	96.84
Mar.	508.42	1110.58	6.97	36.16	27.42	92.14
Apr.	260.64	1057.71	36.00	33.92	28.03	88.88
May	376.50	1018.61	159.55	32.20	27.50	88.34
Jun.	287.32	975.16	196.48	30.40	26.96	87.28
Jul.	546.80	688.58	363.48	29.46	27.19	88.12
Aug.	1412.48	816.48	745.55	31.02	27.34	91.19
Sep.	2283.13	1189.63	658.73	33.95	26.80	100.04
Oct.	1624.20	1535.03	550.37	36.57	26.79	106.80
Nov.	1197.97	1177.17	112.40	37.32	26.57	106.64
Dec.	1230.77	1277.52	54.46	37.62	26.65	104.03

Table 5: Average Inflow Rate and Gross Operating Head for 2015

YEAR 2015						
Month	AVERAGE INFLOW RATE (CUB.M/SEC)			AVERAGE GROSS OPERATING HEAD (M)		
	KAINJI	JEBBA	SHIRORO	Kanji	Jebba	Shiroro
Jan.	1356.32	1360.23	31.59	37.03	26.44	96.58
Feb.	1091.82	1283.14	14.71	36.89	26.44	95.84
Mar.	317.13	1003.26	11.13	35.25	27.24	91.56
Apr.	154.93	864.83	8.07	33.56	27.13	88.13
May	261.95	767.10	13.23	31.87	27.17	88.73
Jun.	220.17	705.00	128.93	30.35	20.62	87.09
Jul.	565.97	526.87	350.10	29.79	27.24	88.50
Aug.	2542.55	945.68	581.58	32.58	28.97	98.83
Sep.	2142.29	1842.00	560.06	34.94	26.58	109.02
Oct.	2022.00	1886.52	613.39	35.84	28.07	110.99
Nov.	1123.80	1215.13	89.10	36.84	27.84	109.85
Dec.	1197.06	1065.35	74.10	38.50	26.57	106.71

Table 6: Average Inflow Rate and Gross Operating Head for 2016

YEAR 2016						
Month	AVERAGE INFLOW RATE (CUB.M/SEC)			AVERAGE GROSS OPERATING HEAD (M)		
	KAINJI	JEBBA	SHIRORO	Kanji	Jebba	Shiroro
Jan.	1358.55	1295.35	42.13	38.30	26.41	103.48
Feb.	1306.17	1321.21	29.66	38.25	26.37	99.78
Mar.	860.48	1333.23	23.49	37.91	26.18	94.72
Apr.	274.23	1095.06	21.23	36.24	26.83	88.45
May	295.84	1203.84	152.32	34.02	26.56	86.29
Jun.	727.29	1404.81	236.55	29.80	25.38	85.00
Jul.	926.23	1509.16	713.29	29.12	26.51	90.45
Aug.	2200.94	1642.21	656.06	29.96	26.89	98.05

Sep.	2269.57	2046.5	299.17	34.71	29.05	106.41
Oct.	2318.26	2139.45	422.65	35.80	27.32	111.10
Nov.	1349.17	1480.77	106.27	36.12	28.58	109.29
Dec.	1367.81	1402.81	73.48	35.98	28.50	106.54

Table 7: Average Inflow Rate and Gross Operating Head for 2017

YEAR 2017						
Month	AVERAGE INFLOW RATE (CUB.M/SEC)			AVERAGE GROSS OPERATING HEAD (M)		
	KAINJI	JEBBA	SHIRORO	Kanji	Jebba	Shiroro
Jan.	1438.10	1332.13	41.87	36.22	28.26	103.02
Feb.	1279.04	1254.43	24.71	36.34	28.52	99.46
Mar.	519.45	1226.45	40.39	36.07	27.93	94.90
Apr.	179.87	1228.23	75.13	33.23	26.36	86.37
May	376.80	1223.74	166.94	32.03	26.40	95.77
Jun.	653.30	1183.63	434.47	29.96	27.15	91.47
Jul.	1534.32	1225.19	604.39	29.88	28.71	102.12
Aug.	2410.45	1898.03	565.58	33.08	28.02	97.98
Sep.	1538.30	2286.40	611.60	35.05	26.36	104.75
Oct.	2049.90	2233.19	288.71	36.53	27.48	109.25
Nov.	1152.77	1233.83	81.47	37.16	28.10	108.24
Dec.	1150.42	1148.61	38.06	37.32	28.25	106.39

Table 8: Summary of Efficiency of various Pumps

Reaction turbines		
Prime Mover	Efficiency Range	Generator Plant
Francis	80-90%	Shiroro and Jebba
Kaplan	80-90%	Kainji

3.2 POWER OUTPUT OF A HYDROPOWER PLANT

The power output of a turbine in a hydropower station, is given by:

$$P_{output} = P_{gross} \times n$$

where

$$P_{gross} = g \times H \times Q$$

(2)

$$\therefore P_{output} = gHQn = 9.81 \times H \times Q \times n$$

(3)

P_{output} = Power output (kW); g = acceleration due to gravity (m/s^2); H = available head (m); Q = turbine flow (m^3/s); n = overall efficiency of the turbine-generator (%).

3.3 CAPACITY FACTOR

- (1) Capacity Factor (CF) is a measure of the usage of the plant. Every plant must have a reserve capacity to take care of the future expansion, i.e. total installed capacity of plant is usually greater than actually required. The CF is expressed as:

$$CF = \frac{\text{Energy generated in a given period}}{\text{Installed capacity of plant} \times \text{number of hours in the given period}}$$

(4)

4.0. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The theoretical power generating capacities of hydropower stations in Nigeria were determined in this study as shown in Figures 3 to 7. Figure 3 shows the monthly power generated in 2013. The average power generated in 2013 by Kainji is 319.37MW (about 42% of installed capacity), Jebba is 268.23MW (about 46% of installed capacity) and Shiroro is 177.64MW (also about 30% of installed capacity).

Figure 4 shows the power generation of 2014, the average power generation for Kainji is 298.03MW (39% of installed capacity), Jebba is 258.71MW (45%

installed capacity) and Shiroro is 197.89MW (33% installed capacity). The average power generated in 2015 as depicted in Figure 5 for Kainji is 317.15MW (42% installed capacity), Jebba is 251.45MW (44% installed capacity) and Shiroro is 176.42MW (29% installed capacity). The power generation in 2016 as indicated in Figure 6 shows that Kainji, Jebba and Shiroro generated 48%, 58% and 31% respectively of their installed capacities. Lastly, Figure 7 for 2017 depicts the average power generation of 344.02MW, 334.66MW and 207.37MW for Kainji, Jebba and Shiroro respectively.

Figure 3: Graph of Power Generation for 2013

Figure 4: Graph of Power Generation 2014

Figure 5: Graph of Power Generation 2015

Figure 6: Graph of Power Generation 2016

Figure 7: Graph of Power Generation 2017

Table 9 shows the plant's capacity factor for the period under review (2013-2017). The average capacity factor for Kainji hydropower station is 43%, with a minimum value of 39% in 2014 and a maximum value of 48% in 2016 as against standard practice of between 50 to 80%. The average CF for Jebba and Shiroro hydropower plants are 50% and 32% respectively, with Shiroro and Jebba stations having a minimum of 29% in 2015 and 44% in 2015 respectively as against best practice of between 50 to 80%. Generally, low CF implies excessive plant

failure which shows that the capacity of the plant was under-utilized for the period under review. Hence, high CF is essential for a viable economic plant operation.

Also, the average plant capacity factor (CF) for Kainji, Jebba and Shiroro hydropower stations was 43%, 50% and 32% respectively as against standard practice of between 50 to 80%. A low CF indicates excessive plant failures, which can be mitigated via proper training for personnel, routine maintenance of plant, proper spare parts inventory and general welfare of staffs.

Table 9: Capacity Factor

KAINJI HYDROPOWER STATION			
YEAR	AVERAGE ENERGY GENERATED (MWH)	PLANT CAPACITY (MWH)	CAPACITY FACTOR (%)
2013	2797681	6657600	42
2014	2610743	6657600	39
2015	2778234	6657600	42
2016	3219563	6657600	48
2017	3013615	6657600	45
AVERAGE	2883967	6657600	43
JEBBA HYDROPOWER STATION			
YEAR	AVERAGE ENERGY GENERATED (MWH)	PLANT CAPACITY (MWH)	CAPACITY FACTOR (%)
2013	2349695	5063280	46
2014	2266300	5063280	45
2015	2202702	5063280	44
2016	2954222	5063280	58
2017	2931622	5063280	58
AVERAGE	2540908	5063280	50
SHIRORO HYDROPOWER STATION			
YEAR	AVERAGE ENERGY GENERATED (MWH)	PLANT CAPACITY (MWH)	CAPACITY FACTOR (%)
2013	1556126	5256000	30
2014	1733516	5256000	33
2015	1545439	5256000	29
2016	1654151	5256000	31
2017	1816561	5256000	35
AVERAGE	1661159	5256000	32

Figure 8: Bar Chart of Capacity Factor

5.0.CONCLUSION

This study has successfully determined the power generation of Kainji, Jebba and Shiroro hydropower stations for the period 2013 to 2017. The calculated power for the hydropower stations can be considered as an important tool for energy planners, systems operators, policy makers, etc. to have an insight on the performance of these plants. The results obtained, reveal the average power generation ranging from 298.03MW to 367.53MW for Kainji, 251.45MW to 337.24MW for Jebba and 176.42MW to 207.37MW for Shiroro. The above generation levels for these three key hydropower stations fall short of the installed capacities, hence, urgent measures need to be put in place to mitigate this short fall anomaly.

REFERENCES

- Abaka, J. U., Ibraheem, T. B., Salmanu, H. and Olokede, O. (2017), "Hydropower potential of Nigeria", *International Journal of Modern Engineering Research*, Vol. 7, pp. 52-58.
- Ajibola, O. O. E., Ajala, O. S., Akanmu, J. O. and Balogun, O. J. (2018),

"Improvement of hydroelectric power generation using pumped storage system", *Nigerian Journal of Technology*, Vol. 37, pp. 191-199.

- Amiryar, M. E. and Pullen, K. R. (2017), "A review of flywheel energy storage system technologies and their applications", *Journal of Applied Sciences*, Vol. 7, pp. 1-21.
- Basso, S. and Botter, G. (2012), "Streamflow variability and optimal capacity of run-of-river hydropower plants", *Water Resources Research*, Vol. 48, pp. 1-13.
- Chiyembekezo, S. K., Cuthbert, Z. K. and Torbjorn, K. N. (2012), "Potential of small-scale hydropower for electric generation in sub-Saharan Africa", *International Scholarly Research Network*, Vol. 2012, pp. 1-15.
- Energy Commission of Nigeria (ECN), *Renewable Energy Master Plan (REMP)*, Abuja, 2005.
- Edeoja, A., Ibrahim, S. and Kucha, E. (2015), "Suitability of Pico-hydropower technology for addressing the Nigerian Energy crisis: A Review", *International Journal of Engineering Inventions*, vol. 4, 17-40.
- Edomah, N., Foulds, C. and Jones, A. (2016), "Energy transitions in Nigeria: The evolution of energy infrastructure provision (1800-

- 2015)", *Journal of Energies*, Vol. 9, pp. 1-18.
- Edomah, N. (2016), "On the path to sustainability: Key issues on Nigeria's sustainable energy development", *Energy Reports* published by Elsevier Ltd, pp. 28-34.
- Fagbohun, O. O. and Omotoso, T. (2018), "Small hydropower viability assessment of Elemi River in Ekiti state of Nigeria", *Journal of Energy Research and Reviews*, Vol. 1, pp. 1-12.
- Gbadamosi, S. L. and Ojo, O. A. (2015), "Dynamic modelling and simulation of shiroro hydropower plant in Nigeria using MATLAB/SIMULINK", *International Journal of Scientific and Engineering Research*, Vol. 6, pp. 948-955.
- Girma, Z. (2016), "Techno-Economic feasibility of small scale hydropower in Ethiopia: The Case of the Kulfo River, in southern Ethiopia", *Journal of Renewable Energy*, Vol. 2016, pp. 1-12.
- Igbinovia S. O. and Orukpe P. E. (2007) "Rural electrification: the propelling force for rural development of Edo State, Nigeria". *Journal of Energy in Southern Africa*, Vol. 18, No. 3, pp. 18-26.
- Mansor, H. (2014), "Power generation methods, techniques and economic strategy", *International Technical Sciences Journal*, Vol. 1, pp. 43-45.
- Mbalisi, O. F. and Offor, B. O. (2015), "Energy crisis and its effects on National development: The need for environmental education in Nigeria", *British Journal of Education*, Vol. 3, pp. 21-37.
- Milnes, M., "The mathematics of pumping water", *The Royal Academy of Engineering*, AECOM Design Build.
- Nwankwo, O. C. and Njogo, B. O. (2013), "The effect of electricity supply on industrial production within the Nigerian economy (1970-2010)", *Journal of Energy Technologies and Policy*, Vol. 3, pp. 34-42.
- Ogundipe, A. A. and Apata, A. (2013), "Electricity consumption and economic growth in Nigeria", *Journal of Business Management and Applied Economics*, Vol. 2, pp. 1-14.
- Ohunakin, O. S., Ojolo, S. J. and Ajayi, O. O. (2011), "Small hydropower (SHP) development in Nigeria: An assessment", *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, Elsevier, Vol. 15, pp. 2006-2013.
- Okeola, O. G. and Balogun, O. S. (2017), "Challenges and contradictions in Nigeria's water resources policy development: A critical review", *International Journal of Science and Technology*, Bahir Dar-Ethiopia, Vol. 6, pp. 1-19.
- Onyenekenwa, C. E. (2011), "Nigeria's vision 20:2020-issues, challenges and implications for development management", *Asian Journal of Rural Development*, Vol. 1, pp. 21-40.
- Othman, A., Khairudin, W. M., Othman, J., Ghani, M. A. and Saudi, A. S. M. (2017), "Water flow measuring methods in small hydropower for streams and rivers-A study", *International Journal of Applied Engineering Research*, Vol. 12, pp. 14484-14489.
- Otuagama, S. O., Ogujor, E. A. and Kuale, P. A. (2016), "Determination of head for small hydropower development: A case study of River Ethiopie at Umutu, Nigeria", *Nigerian Journal of Technology*, Vol. 35, pp. 190-195.
- Oyedepo, S. O. (2012), "Energy and sustainable development in Nigeria: The way forward", *Journal of Energy, Sustainability and Society*, Vol. 2, pp. 1-17.
- Salami, A. W., Sule, B. F., Adunkpe, T. L., Ayanshola, A. M. and Bilewu, S. O. (2017), "Evaluation of the hydropower generation potential of a dam using optimization techniques:

- Application to Doma Dam, Nassarawa, in North Central Nigeria”, *Slovak Journal of Civil Engineering*, Vol. 25, pp. 1-9.
- Sambo, A. S. (2008), “Matching electricity supply with demand in Nigeria”, *International Association for Energy Economics*, Fourth Quarter, pp. 32-36.
- Shobayo, D. I., Adejumobi, O. A., Awolola, O. S. and Akinwale, A. T. (2014), “An assessment of the small hydro potential of Opeki River, Southwestern Nigeria”, *Science Journal of Energy Engineering*, Vol. 2, pp. 25-31.